

mination based on its diazotisation and subsequent coupling with salicylic acid.

Experimental

A Cari-Zeiss spekol spectrophotometer with 1-cm path-length was used.

A stock solution (1 mg ml⁻¹) of benzidine in 20% ethanol and 0.06 M HCl was prepared. A working standard of 10 µg ml⁻¹ was used. A sodium nitrite solution of 200 µg ml⁻¹ strength was used. A 2% (w/v) solution of salicylic acid was prepared in 0.3 M NaOH. All reagents used were of A.R. grade.

Procedure: To a sample containing 5–25 µg of benzidine in 10-ml volumetric flask, sodium nitrite solution (1 ml) and 2 M HCl (1 ml) were added in succession and the mixture was left for 2 min. Then solutions of salicylic acid (1 ml) and 4 M NaOH (0.5 ml) were added and the volume was made upto the mark with demineralised water. The solution was kept for 10 min at room temperature for full colour development and the absorbance was measured at 480 nm against water.

Results and Discussion

The orange dye having maximum absorbance at 480 nm was stable for ~48 h.

Acidity: 1 min was sufficient for complete diazotisation in presence of 0.2–5 M HCl. An amount of 0.3–0.6 ml of 4 M NaOH in 10 ml sample was needed for full colour development.

Analytical characteristics: Beer's law was obeyed in the concentration range 0.5–2.5 ppm with molar absorptivity of $5.7 \times 10^4 \text{ dm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and Sandell's sensitivity $0.0032 \text{ } \mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$, respectively. The standard deviation and coefficient of variation were found to be 0.006 and 1.04% respectively for 10 µg of benzidine in 10 ml of the solution.

Effect of foreign species: The tolerance limits (in ppm) for various foreign species associated with benzidine (1 ppm) are as follows: *p*-Nitroaniline, *o*-nitroaniline, phenol (5), aniline, formaldehyde (25), nitrobenzene, chlorobenzene (100), *o*-, *m*-, *p*-nitrotoluene, diphenylamine, pyridine (160), hydrocarbons (1000): Al^{III}, Cu^{II} (160), Ba^{II}, Pb^{II}, Fe^{III}, Cr^{III} (150), Mg^{II}, Ca^{II}, chloride, nitrate, phosphate, sulphate (300); metal ions forming hydroxide in alkaline medium were masked with 1 ml of 10% Na₂-EDTA. Some amines interfered but in high concentration.

Application: The method can be reliably applied for the determination of benzidine in urine and polluted water samples with ~95% and ~100% of recovery, respectively.

Data in Table 1 presents the superiority of this method over the reported ones^{3,4}.

TABLE 1

Method	λ_{max} (nm)	Molar absorptivity $\times 10^4 \text{ dm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$
α -Naphthol ^a	585	4.48
8-Hydroxyquinoline ^b	500	3.80
Salicylic acid ^c	480	5.70

^a Ref. 3. ^b Ref. 4. ^c Present work.

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Isolation and Identification of Barbiturates in Biological Material by Thin Layer Chromatography

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THIN layer chromatography has been widely used as a rapid and simple screening method for phenobarbital¹. The present paper describes a rapid method for the identification and estimation of barbiturates by means of tlc and its application towards the study of barbiturates in biological fluids. The process of isolation and identification is based on acid hydrolysis of barbiturates. The derivatives are analysed by tlc.

Standard tlc equipment and A. R. grade reagents were used. Stationary phase was silica gel G (0.25 mm) on glass plates (20 × 30 cm), and mobile phases were methanol-chloroform and benzyl alcohol-

methanol. The following visualising reagents were used. (i) Zwikker reagent^a: The plate after being sprayed with 1% solution of cobalt(II) nitrate in absolute ethanol, was dried at room temperature and introduced into a chamber saturated with water vapour containing 25% ammonium hydroxide solution, (ii) Cobalt nitrate-lithium hydroxide reagent^a: The plate was sprayed with spray reagent-I (2% cobalt(II) nitrate in anhydrous methanol) dried in air and then with spray reagent-II (0.5% lithium hydroxide in methanol). (iii) Mercurous nitrate reagent^a: A 1% aqueous mercurous nitrate and (iv) Fluorescein-ammonia reagent^a: For purins, pyrimidines and barbiturates 0.005% soln. of fluorescein in 0.5 N NH₄OH) were used. The chromatogram was examined in long and short wave uv light.

Process: The unhydrolysed drug (10 g) was heated on a boiling-water-bath with 6 N HCl (10 ml) for 1 h. The solution was then made alkaline with ammonia (pH 8) and the drug was extracted with ether. The organic fraction was evaporated to dryness and the residue dissolved in ethanol (10 ml).

The drugs were given in microgram to the albino rats of young age. After 4 h, its kidney, heart and brain were taken out and urine and blood samples were collected separately. To detect barbiturates in organs and body fluids, they were first concentrated and purified in the procedure preceding tlc separation.

The material was extracted with ethanol, the residue taken up in water, the solution acidified with tartaric acid and the barbituric acids were extracted with ether. Any strongly acid contaminants which are extracted at the same time may be separated by shaking the ether solution with a sodium acetate-acetic acid buffer (pH 4.4). The pre-purification of barbiturates to be isolated from urine can likewise be carried out by acid-ether extraction. Barbiturates were extracted from blood with chloroform instead of ether.

Procedure: The silica gel G (0.25 mm thickness) glass plate (20×30 cm) was dried and activated at 120° for 60 min before its use. Separate spots of extracted drugs and pure drugs were applied on the plate and it was run in the solvent system of chloroform-xylene-acetone (80:130:90). After 25 cm of the run the plate was exposed to air, and subsequently sprayed with Zwikker reagents, mercurous nitrate, cobalt(II) nitrate and fluorescein solutions as described before. The results are presented in Table 1.

TABLE 1—R_f VALUE* AND COLOUR OF DIFFERENT METABOLITES** OF BARBITONE AND DIETHYL BARBITONE ON TLC PLATE[‡]

Dose=200 µg, solvent system=chloroform-xylene-acetone (8:18:2), solvent front movement=25 cm, temp.=22°, time=2 h, humidity=70%

Sl. no.	Tissue	R _f *	R _f *	
1.	Drug	0.51 ^a	0.42 ^b	
	Liver	0.94	0.92	
2.		0.79	0.69	
		0.69	0.44	
		0.46	0.98	
		0.86	0.26	
		0.28		
	3.	Kidney	0.95	0.88
			0.85	0.65
			0.78	0.44
0.71			0.18	
4.	Brain	0.34		
		0.21	0.90	
		0.98	0.69	
		0.82	0.55	
		0.69	0.44	
		0.34	0.18	
5.	Urine	0.20		
		0.98	0.92	
		0.44	0.44	
6.	Blood	0.34		
			0.90	
			0.42	

* Colour of the spot in all the cases: ^abarbitone: with fluorescein, light green against pink background and with mercurous nitrate, white against yellow background, ^bdiethylbarbitone: with fluorescein, pink; with mercurous nitrate, white.

**Weight of rat used: for barbitone=100 g, for diethylbarbitone=110 g.

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